

STATE AND LAW

CERTAIN ELEMENTS OF THE MECHANISM FOR REALIZATION OF HUMAN RIGHTS IN PLACES OF DETENTION OF THE STATE BORDER SERVICE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the issue of the mechanism for realization of human rights in places of detention of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine. The author establishes that the rights of persons held in places of detention traditionally remain at high risk of violations. The closure of such institutions, limited public access, dependence of prisoners on the administration, lack of an adequate mechanism for monitoring the observance of rights - all this creates an environment where systemic abuses are possible, including inadequate conditions of detention, ill-treatment, and arbitrariness of officials. The author concludes that Ukraine, striving for membership in the European Union, should adapt its national legal system to the highest standards of human rights protection, which involves improving legislation, strengthening control and prevention mechanisms, and empowering human rights institutions such as the Ombudsman, public monitoring commissions, and international organizations. The author provides his own definition of the concept of the mechanism for the realization of human rights, in particular, it is an integral system of legal means, institutional elements and socio-legal factors that ensure the actual implementation of human rights and freedoms in public relations. It includes legal acts, law enforcement procedures, activities of public authorities, international legal guarantees, as well as social and economic conditions necessary for the effective implementation of and protection of human rights. This view is based on a combination of regulatory and protective mechanisms that ensure not only the possibility of exercising rights but also their protection in case of violation. It also takes into account the role of law enforcement entities - both the holders of rights themselves and state and non-state institutions that facilitate their implementation. Currently, there are two types of migrant detention facilities under the jurisdiction of the SBGS: temporary detention centers and special facilities. In addition to these facilities, the places of detention under the control of the SBGS also include minibuses for the transportation of offenders, where persons can be temporarily detained during transportation. Areas for transit passengers at international airports, where persons who are denied entry or awaiting a decision on their legal status may be held. Recommendations are made to improve certain mechanisms for the realization of human rights in places of detention of the SBGS.

Keywords: realization of human rights, places of detention, State Border Guard Service of Ukraine, temporary detention centers, special premises.

Statement of the problem. The study of human rights, especially the mechanisms for their realization in places of detention, is not only relevant but also vital in the current context. Ukraine is experiencing difficult challenges caused by armed aggression, reform of law enforcement and penitentiary systems, and integration into the European legal space, which requires a rethinking of approaches to ensuring human rights, including those of vulnerable groups. The rights of persons held in places of detention traditionally remain at high risk of violations. The closure of such institutions, limited public access, dependence of prisoners on the administration, lack of a proper mechanism for monitoring the observance of rights

- all this creates an environment where systemic abuses are possible, including inadequate conditions of detention, ill-treatment, and arbitrariness of officials. In the context of armed conflict, these problems are exacerbated even more, as prisoners of war, civilian hostages, and persons illegally detained in the temporarily occupied territories are added to the category of persons deprived of their liberty. The issue of their protection, documentation of violations, and international legal response is of paramount importance to the state. At the same time, Ukraine, striving for

membership in the European Union, must adapt its national legal system to the highest standards of human rights protection, which involves improving legislation, strengthening control and prevention mechanisms, and empowering human rights institutions such as the Ombudsman, public monitoring commissions, and international organizations. Particular attention should be paid to the effectiveness of national remedies, as even the existence of a developed international monitoring system, such as the European Court of Human Rights, cannot replace effective domestic mechanisms. Prevention of torture, ensuring the right to proper treatment, access to legal aid and fair trial are key aspects that determine the level of democratic maturity of a state. In the context of global changes, growing authoritarian tendencies in the world, migration crises, international armed conflicts and hybrid threats, the issue of human rights protection in places of detention is becoming an indicator of the civilization of the state, its ability to adhere to the rule of law, and guarantee the rights of even those under the control of state authorities. That is why this area of research is not just relevant, it is crucial for the future of Ukraine's legal system and its place in the international community

Analysis of recent research. Scientific research

devoted to defining the essence of the concept of "place of detention" has not yet received a comprehensive and integrated study in Ukrainian legal science. At the same time, in the works of such scholars as A. I. Bogatyryova, I. G. Bogatyryova, O. M. Bandurka, V. V. Kovalenko, O. M. Dzhuzha, O. G. Kolb, M. S. Puzryev, I. M. Kopotun, V. M. Trubnikov, M. O. Struchkov, I. V. Shmarov, A. Kh. Stepaniuk, S. I. Khalimon, I. S. Yakovets and others, highlight certain aspects of this issue, in particular, issues related to the legal status of places of detention and their correlation with the category of places of detention. In addition, the issue of ensuring human and civil rights and freedoms remains in the focus of attention of contemporary Ukrainian scholars. In particular, a significant contribution to its research was made by such scholars as V. B. Averyanov, O. F. Andriyko, V. M. Beschastnyi, O. V. Zaychuk, AP. Zayets, S. Husarev, A. Kolodiy, V. Kopechykov, M. Kozyubra, R. Kalyuzhny, V. Kurylo, N. Onishchenko, P. Onopenko, V. Pohorilko, V. Petkov, P. Rabinovych, Y. Shemshuchenko and others. Their scientific works cover various aspects of this topic, including theoretical and legal foundations, constitutional guarantees, mechanisms for the realization and protection of human rights in Ukraine.

Summary of the main material. The term "mechanism" has several meanings. In the literal sense, it is a system of moving elements designed to transmit or convert motion. In a figurative sense, a mechanism means the internal structure and system of functioning of a certain phenomenon or process [1].

In the context of jurisprudence, a mechanism means the internal structure of a legal phenomenon, which includes interconnected elements that form a system. The legal doctrine widely uses the concepts of "mechanism of realization of law", "mechanism of ensuring human rights", "mechanism of fulfillment of constitutional duties", etc. An important aspect of the study is to clarify the essence and features of these mechanisms [2, P. 13-19].

According to M.D. Hnatiuk, the mechanism of implementation of law is a specific subsystem of legal regulation, which includes regulatory and protective means that ensure the implementation of legal norms in the actual behavior of subjects [3, P. 5, 10]. O.F. Skakun interprets the socio-legal mechanism for ensuring human rights and freedoms as a system of means and factors that create conditions for the realization of these rights [4, P. 207].

Y.M. Todika defines the mechanism of implementation of constitutional norms as a set of legal and institutional elements that ensure practical implementation of constitutional provisions [5, P. 339]. At the same time, there is literature, the authors of which consider the mechanism of rights realization through the prism of guarantees. Thus, the guarantees of human and civil rights and freedoms constitute a set of legal norms, organizational mechanisms and procedures enshrined in the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, which ensure effective realization, protection and defense of individual rights. In the constitutional and legal dimension, they are divided into regulatory and organizational guarantees. Regulatory and legal

guarantees include a set of legal norms that define the procedure for the realization of rights and freedoms, mechanisms for their protection and liability for their violation. They cover constitutional principles, legal obligations of the state to citizens and the system of legal liability. Organizational and legal guarantees cover the activities of state bodies, local self-government, courts, political parties, public organizations, mass media, as well as international human rights institutions aimed at creating conditions for the full exercise of citizens' rights and freedoms [6]. O.F. Melnychuk considers the mechanism of realization of the human right to education as a complex of general social and legal means, including the activities of authorized persons, regulations, legal facts and guarantees of implementation [7, P. 27].

Taking into account the views of legal scholars on the understanding of the mechanism of human rights realization, we believe that the mechanism of human rights realization is an integral system of legal means, institutional elements and socio-legal factors that ensure the actual implementation of human rights and freedoms in public relations. It includes legal acts, law enforcement procedures, activities of public authorities, international legal guarantees, as well as social and economic conditions necessary for the effective exercise and protection of human rights. This view is based on a combination of regulatory and protective mechanisms that ensure not only the possibility of realizing rights but also their protection in case of violation. It also takes into account the role of law enforcement actors - both the holders of rights themselves and the state and non-state institutions that facilitate their implementation.

We consider it necessary, within the framework of this study, to consider certain components of the mechanism for the realization of human rights in places of detention, on the example of temporary detention centers and special premises of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine.

In a democratic state governed by the rule of law, ensuring national security and territorial integrity is inextricably linked to the observance of human rights and freedoms. The State Border Guard Service of Ukraine (SBGS) performs a key function - protecting the state border - which necessitates certain restrictions on human rights, including the right to liberty and security of person. Such restrictions are lawful and justified if they comply with the principles of proportionality, legality and necessity in a democratic society. They are provided for by both national legislation (the Constitution of Ukraine, laws regulating border control) and international standards, in particular the European Convention on Human Rights. In particular, according to the current legislation, border guards have the right to detain persons who have violated the state border regime, to check documents and apply coercive measures in cases specified by law [8]. At the same time, such actions should be aimed exclusively at achieving the legitimate goal of ensuring the security of the state and citizens, countering illegal migration, smuggling and other threats. Thus, the activities of the State Border Guard Service combine law enforcement and human rights,

which is a necessary component of the rule of law.

The State Border Guard Service of Ukraine (SBGS) is authorized to carry out administrative detention of persons in accordance with the applicable law. This applies, in particular, to foreigners and stateless persons who have illegally crossed the state border of Ukraine and in respect of whom a decision has been made to transfer them to the competent authorities of a neighboring state. The duration of detention is determined by law and is limited to the time required to complete the relevant procedures. Persons detained under the administrative procedure must be held in specially equipped premises that meet the established standards. Currently, there are two types of migrant detention facilities under the jurisdiction of the SBGS: temporary detention centers - designed to accommodate persons who have illegally crossed the state border or violated the regime of stay in Ukraine until the issue of their return or expulsion is resolved. Special premises - used for temporary accommodation of detainees until they are transferred to the relevant competent authorities. In addition to these facilities, the places of detention under the control of the SBGS also include minibuses for the transportation of offenders, where persons may be temporarily detained during transportation. Areas for transit passengers at international airports, where persons who are denied entry or awaiting a decision on their legal status may be held [9, P. 122-125]. The functioning of such institutions is regulated by national legislation and must comply with international human rights standards, including guarantees of proper treatment of detainees and respect for their rights.

The regulatory and legal component of the mechanism for the realization of human rights in the above-mentioned places of detention is the current legislation of Ukraine, of which the Constitution of Ukraine has the highest legal force. The provisions of the Constitution of Ukraine that lay down fundamental legal guarantees for the realization of human and civil rights and freedoms include the following:

- Immutability of fundamental rights - no amendments to the Constitution may provide for their abolition or restriction.
- The duty of the state to respect and protect human rights.
- Direct effect of constitutional provisions that enshrine rights and freedoms.
- Legal liability for violations of citizens' rights for both authorities and officials.
- The right to self-defense by all legal means.
- Guarantees of legal assistance and judicial protection.
- Democratic principles of justice and ensuring humane treatment of detainees.
- Functioning of special bodies, in particular the Constitutional Court, to protect rights.
- Other guarantees arising from the democratic system of government and the state's socio-economic policy. These mechanisms form the legal basis for the realization and protection of human rights in Ukraine,

ensuring stability and the rule of law [10].

Among the existing legal guarantees of human rights protection, the most important is judicial protection. The Constitution of Ukraine (part 3 of Article 8) guarantees everyone the right to go to court to protect their constitutional rights and freedoms directly on the basis of the Basic Law [10]. Citizens may appeal in court against decisions, actions or omissions of state authorities, local self-government bodies, as well as officials and employees. Since Ukraine's independence, the judicial system has undergone significant positive changes. Key laws regulating the judicial system and court proceedings, in particular, have been adopted and updated: Law of Ukraine "On the Judiciary and Status of Judges" (2016); Law of Ukraine "On Access to Court Decisions" (2005); Law of Ukraine "On the Execution of Judgments and Application of the Case Law of the European Court of Human Rights" (2006); Civil Procedure Code of Ukraine (2004); Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine (2012); and other legal acts. Despite these reforms, judicial protection of human rights in Ukraine faces a number of problems, including: low level of public confidence in the judicial system due to delays in trials, lack of transparency of procedures and inconsistency of court decisions; corruption risks in the judicial system that undermine the efficiency and objectivity of legal proceedings; insufficient use by Ukrainian courts of the case law of the European Court of Human Rights (ECHR), which limits the effectiveness of legal protection and harmonization of national legislation with European standards [11, P. 31]. Improvement of the situation requires further reforms aimed at strengthening the independence of judges, ensuring proper financing of the judicial system, raising the legal culture of the population and more active implementation of ECHR judgments in judicial practice.

An important element of the national mechanism for the realization of human rights in places of detention of the SBGS is the work of the Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights, which operates within the framework of the National Preventive Mechanism.

The Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights plays a key role in monitoring the observance of human rights, especially in places of detention. His right to freely visit such institutions provides an effective mechanism for monitoring the conditions of detention, compliance with the law and protection of their rights.

Given the wide range of places subject to inspection, the Commissioner's activities are aimed not only at combating violations of the rights of detained or convicted persons, but also at protecting the rights of children, persons with disabilities, the elderly and other vulnerable groups. This ensures transparency of the activities of state bodies and promotes the implementation of European human rights standards in Ukraine. The Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights has broad powers to protect human and civil rights and freedoms. In accordance with the procedure established by law, he/she has the right to apply to the court in the interests of persons who, due

to their physical condition, underage, old age, incapacity or limited capacity, are unable to protect their rights and freedoms on their own. The Commissioner may participate in court proceedings initiated by his/her claims, applications or petitions, as well as enter into court proceedings at any stage of their consideration if they are initiated by other persons. In addition, he has the right to initiate a review of court decisions regardless of his participation in the proceedings. Such powers ensure effective control over the observance of human rights and freedoms in Ukraine and contribute to the formation of a state governed by the rule of law, where judicial protection of every citizen is guaranteed [12].

Given the importance of this element of the mechanism, we believe it needs to be improved. In order to improve the activities of the Ukrainian Parliament Commissioner for Human Rights within the mechanism for the realization of human rights in places of detention, comprehensive changes should be introduced to improve the effectiveness of monitoring, ensure the independence of the institution and strengthen the mechanisms for responding to human rights violations. First, the institutional capacity of the Ombudsperson should be expanded by creating specialized units focusing on different categories of places of detention, including penitentiary institutions, pre-trial detention centers, special facilities for migrants, psychiatric institutions and children's boarding schools. This will allow for a more in-depth analysis of the conditions of detention and identification of systemic problems. Secondly, it is necessary to strengthen the independence of monitoring visits by expanding the access of civil society organizations to inspect places of detention together with representatives of the Ombudsperson. Such a mechanism will help to increase transparency and reduce the risks of inaccurate coverage of the real situation. Thirdly, it is necessary to enshrine in law the mandatory implementation of the Commissioner's recommendations by state and local authorities. Currently, such recommendations are mostly advisory in nature, which often leads to their ignoring. The introduction of enforcement mechanisms, for example, by imposing administrative liability for failure to comply with the Commissioner's instructions, will help to have a real impact on the situation in places of detention. Fifthly, an important aspect is to strengthen the protection of whistleblowers of human rights violations in places of detention, including staff of institutions and detainees themselves. The introduction of anonymous complaint mechanisms with a guarantee of protection from harassment will be an important step in this direction. In general, effective reform of the mechanism of realization of human rights in places of detention is possible only with a comprehensive approach that combines strengthening the powers of the Ombudsperson, improving legislative regulation and ensuring real impact on the human rights protection processes.

The European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms and the case law of the European Court of Human Rights play a key role in the mechanism of realization of human rights in

places of detention of the SBGS. The application of the provisions of the European Convention on Human Rights and the case law of the European Court of Human Rights is of great importance for Ukraine, its authorities and citizens. Since the country has chosen the path of European integration, is seeking to join the European Union, is strengthening its international authority and reinforcing the principles of the rule of law both domestically and internationally, this requires strict compliance with the ECHR and the implementation of the ECtHR judgments. In this context, it is important to determine the place of the ECHR in the national legal order. According to Article 9 of the Constitution of Ukraine, international treaties ratified by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine are part of national legislation [10]. As the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine ratified the "Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950 and its Protocols", the provisions of the ECHR became part of national legislation [13]. In addition, according to Article 19 of the Law of Ukraine "On International Treaties of Ukraine", international treaties ratified by the Verkhovna Rada are part of national legislation and are applied in the same way as domestic law [14]. It is important to note that if an international treaty ratified by Ukraine provides for different rules than national legislation, the rules of the international treaty shall apply, which gives it greater legal force [14].

ECHR case law is also important for the national legal system. According to Article 17 of the Law of Ukraine "On the Execution of Judgments and Application of the Case Law of the European Court of Human Rights", courts are obliged to apply the ECHR case law as a source of law when deciding cases related to the ECHR [15]. Article 5 of this law also provides that central executive authorities shall monitor compliance with administrative practice that is consistent with the ECHR and the case law of the ECtHR [15]. Also, Article 32 of the ECHR states that the jurisdiction of the ECtHR extends to all questions of interpretation and application of the ECHR and its protocols submitted for examination under Articles 33, 34, 46 and 47 [16]. The problematic issue with the effectiveness of this element is, of course, that the very fact of applying to the ECtHR indicates human rights violations, including in places of detention [17]. In addition, a significant part of the ECHR judgments are not implemented by Ukraine, which indicates systemic gaps in the protection of human rights in places of detention [18].

Conclusions. Having carried out this study, we have come to the conclusion that the mechanism for the realization of human rights in places of detention, in particular in the context of the activities of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine (SBGS), is extremely important for ensuring the dignity and rights of all persons under state control. The effective realization of human rights in such conditions guarantees compliance with the standards set forth in international agreements, in particular the European Convention on Human Rights, and ensures the prevention of violations of the rights of detainees. The importance of such a mechanism lies in the fact that it contributes to maintaining the rule of law, strengthening trust in public authorities and ensuring Ukraine's international

image as a state governed by the rule of law. Taking human rights into account in places of detention is also an important component of reforming Ukraine's legal system to meet European standards and facilitate integration into the European community. Of course, we have analyzed only certain elements of the mechanism for realizing human rights in places of detention of the SBGS, but this made it possible to talk about the imperfection of such mechanisms and pointed to the need to improve them.

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